

Product and Services of ORACLE CORPORATION

Basheema Parveen and Dhanushree

College of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore-India.

E-mail : basheemabachhi@gmail.com

Abstract

Oracle Corporation is an American multinational computer technology corporation, Larry Ellison co-founded Oracle Corporation in 1977 with Bob Miner and Ed Oates under the name Software Development Laboratories. The company specializes in developing and marketing cloud engineered systems and enterprise software products, database software and technology, notably its own brands of database management systems. It offers human capital and talent management, offers chain management, project portfolio management, enterprise resource planning, client experience and relationship management, business analytics and enterprise performance management, and industry-specific application software, as well as financial management. Oracle has embedded innovative technologies in each side of cloud, allowing companies to reimagine their businesses, processes, and experiences. With the introduction of Oracle Autonomous info, the industry's only self-securing, self-driving and self-repairing database. Oracle is again revolutionizing how data is managed. Oracle has designed and developed a Monitoring Cloud service and Social Engagement that enables businesses to capture relevant whole communication from global web and social channels to understand commentary on their products. The Oracle Corporation employed around 137,000 full-time employees globally. Today, 430,000 customers in hundred seventy five countries use Oracle technologies to seize business opportunities and solve real, tangible challenges.

In this paper, we analysed the business strategy of Oracle by studying its operational level and business level strategies including operational strategy, services strategy, technology adoption strategy, HR strategies, marketing strategies, financial strategy, and new product development strategies. We have analysed the business strategy of the corporate utilizing SWOT analysis framework.

Keywords: Case Study, Services, Operation, Technology, Business strategy of IT Company, Careers.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Oracle corporation is founded in 1977 is an American Multinational Computer Technology Corporation was co-founded by Larry Ellison with Bob Miner and Ed Oates. Oracle has 1,37,000 employees which includes 38,000 developers and engineers, 14,000 services specialists who can speak 29 languages and include 19,000 implementation consultants. It has 430,000 customers

around 175 countries and also 25,000 partners. Oracle manufactures, designs and sells software and hardware products, and also services that complement them like training, financing, consulting, and hosting services. It has software as a service, Platform as a service, Infrastructure as a service and other services such as Oracle Consulting- technical business expert services, Oracle Support, Oracle Financing etc. Oracle and also the German

company SAP had a long history of cooperation from 1988, starting with the combination of SAP's enterprise application suite with Oracle's RB products like Microsoft SQL Server, a competition to Oracle Database.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- To find the products and also services supplied by the company.
- To understand finance and business strategy of company.
- To understand the corporate social responsibilities of the company..
- To find the competitors of the company.
- To analyze the overall growth of the company.

3. PRODUCTS AND SERVICES:

Oracle manufactures, designs and sells both hardware and software products, and also services such as training, consulting, financing and hosting services.

Software: Oracle Software Delivery Cloud provides generic downloadable Oracle software and documentation.

Databases:

Oracle Database

Berkeley DB, offers embedded database processing.

Oracle Rdb, may be a computer database system running on OpenVMS platforms.

Middleware: Oracle Fusion Middleware is a family of middleware software products, including application server, system integration, business process management , user interaction, identity management and business intelligence products.

Oracle Secure Enterprise Search: Oracle Secure Enterprise Search , Oracle's enterprise- search, offering, gives users the ability to search for content across multiple locations, including websites, file servers, XML files, enterprise resource planning systems, content management systems, customer relationship management systems, business intelligence systems, and databases.

Applications: Oracle additionally sells a collection of business Applications. The Oracle E-Business Suite includes software to perform various enterprise functions related to financials, manufacturing, customer relationship management, enterprise resource planning and human resource management. The Oracle Retail Suite provide merchandise management, price management, invoice matching, allocations, store operations management, warehouse management, demand forecasting, merchandise financial planning, assortment planning and category management. Users could access these facilities through a browser interface over the net.

Oracle Fusion Application

Oracle Social Engagement and Monitoring System Oracle E-Business Suite

Development software: Oracle Corporation's tools for developing applications:

Oracle Designer - a Case tool that combines with Oracle Developer Suite

Oracle Developer – that consists of Oracle Discoverer, Oracle Forms and Oracle Reports Oracle JDeveloper, a freeware IDE

NetBeans - a Java-based software-development platform Oracle Application Express – also known as APEX

Oracle SQL Developer - an integrated development environment for working together with SQL-based databases

Oracle SQL*Plus Worksheet - a component of Oracle Enterprise Manager Open Java Development Kit

File systems: ZFS combines file-system and logical volume management practically.

Operating systems: Oracle Corporation develops and supports 2 operating systems: Oracle Linux and Oracle Solaris.

Hardware:

- Engineered systems: pre-engineered and pre-assembled hardware/software bundles for enterprise use
- Exadata Database Machine – software/hardware integrated storage
- Exalogic Elastic Cloud – software/hardware integrated application server
- Exalytics In-Memory Machine – software/hardware integrated in-memory analytics server
- Oracle Database Appliance
- Big Data Appliance – integrated map-reduce big data solution

SERVICES:

Oracle cloud: Oracle Cloud provides Platform as a Service, Infrastructure as a Service, Data as a Service and Software as a Service.

Software as a Service:

Enterprise applications: EPM, SCM, ERP, HCM and CX offerings

Platform as a Service :

Oracle has marked its Platform as a Service, as Oracle Cloud Platform. Oracle Cloud Platform offerings embrace Application Development, Data Management, Integration, Content and Experience, Business Analytics, Management and Security.

Platform services on that to make and extend SaaS applications or deploy applications: big data, Java application server, business analytics, mobile, database, integration, process, Internet of Things,

Infrastructure as a Service:

- Oracle has marked its Infrastructure as a Service as . Oracle Cloud Infrastructure offerings include:
- Compute Service
- Storage Service
- Network Service

Other services:

- Oracle Consulting technical and business expert services
- Oracle Financing
- Oracle Support
- Oracle Configuration Manager gathers and uploads details of the organization of Oracle software.
- My Oracle Support Community
- Oracle University (training in Oracle products)
- Oracle Certification Program

4. FINANCE AND MARKETING:

Finances:

Development since 2005

Year	Revenue in mil.US-\$	Net Income in mil.US-\$	Price per Share in US-\$	Employees
2005	11,799	2,886	11.45	
2006	14,380	3,381	13.60	
2007	17,996	4,274	17.41	74,670
2008	22,430	5,521	17.86	84,230
2009	23,252	5,593	18.03	86,000
2010	26,820	6,135	23.02	105,000
2011	35,622	8,547	28.56	108,000
2012	37,121	9,981	27.37	115,000
2013	37,180	10,925	31.28	120,000
2014	38,275	10,955	37.72	122,000
2015	38,226	9,938	38.85	132,000
2016	37,047	8,901	37.94	136,000
2017	37,728	9,335	45.70	138,000

Oracle ranked No. 82 within the 2018 Fortune five hundred list of the biggest US firms by total revenue. According to Bloomberg, Oracle's Chief executive officer to worker pay ratio is 1,205:1. The CEO's compensation in 2017 was \$108,295,023. Meanwhile, the median employee compensation rate was \$89,887.

Marketing:

In 1990, Oracle laid off about 400 people of its work force because of accounting errors. This crisis came as a result of Oracle's "up-front" selling strategy, during which sales people urged potential clients to shop for the biggest possible amount of software all at once. The sales people then engaged the worth of future license sales within the current quarter, thereby increasing their bonuses. This became a issue when the future marketing subsequently failed to materialize. Oracle

had to restate its earnings double, and also settled class-action lawsuits arising from its having overstated its earnings. Ellison stated in 1992 that Oracle created "an unimaginable business mistake."

5. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES:

Oracle is creating history by building a home for a public college at its headquarters and facilitate students develop the technical acumen and artistic confidence essential to innovation—because breakthroughs are built on the foundational concept that despite matter, an answer are often found. Oracle continue to raise the bar around water conservation. By leveraging a wide range of water-saving strategies across our facilities and have achieved a consistent year-over-year reduction in our total water use. Oracle exceeded their 2016 goal to reduce potable water use per employee by 15 percent.

6. COMPETITORS:

- IBM is a top competitor of Oracle Corporation. IBM is a top technology brand. It is a international company that was established in the year 1911 and is headquartered in New York, United States. IBM stands for International Business Machines Corporation. It has its business operations in around 170 countries, across the world. It is ranked as 6th worldwide with respect to the technology sector. It has a complete worth of around \$31.786 billion. IBM has a large focus and facility for R&D to fulfil the demands of the technology and because of which it's a Oracle's top competitor.

- Microsoft, Oracle's another top competitor, is an American multinational company that was formed during the year 1975 and is headquartered in Washington, United States. Its main business operations contain manufacturing, development, licensing, support, and sale of a computer system, electronics, and services. It has a powerful analysis and development activity that prioritize innovation. It has a wonderful product portfolio and due to which it is it is considered as a top Oracle competitor.

- Another top Oracle competitor, SAP is a German technology company that was established during the year 1972 and is headquartered in Germany. SAP is that the abbreviation for Systems, Applications, and Products. SAP has its business operations in around one hundred eighty countries and has about 335,000 customers. The company has around 91,000 workers operating for them. SAP has several innovative product and is high on analysis and development. It has an excellent position within the market and because of that it is considered as top Oracle competitor.

7. ANALYSIS:

The Oracle Corporation is one of the best leading corporation in its industry. Oracle Corporation maintains its position in market by researching and evaluating the SWOT analysis. SWOT is an interactive process and needs effective coordination among numerous departments among the organization like – finance, operations, marketing, management information systems and strategic designing.

Strengths:

1. Good returns on Capital Expenditure
2. Excellent Performance in New Markets
3. Strong Brand Portfolio
4. Strong dealer community
5. Reliable suppliers

Weakness:

1. Not highly successful at combining firms with different work culture.

2. financial planning is not done properly and efficiently.
3. Investment in Analysis and Development is under the fastest growing players in the industry.

Opportunities:

1. Starting up of new markets due to government agreement.
2. New customers from online channel.
3. free cash flow give opportunities to invest in adjoining product segments.

Threats:

1. No regular supply of new products.
2. New technologies designed by the competitor or market disruptor can be a critical threat to the industry in medium to long term future.
3. Changing consumer buying behavior from online channel can be a threat to the existing physical infrastructure driven supply chain model.

8. CONCLUSION:

Despite competition from other leading companies, Oracle Corporation still maintained the standard of products and services which they provide to the world. Oracle predicts the longer term of computing within the cloud. The enterprise software corporate offers a variety of cloud- based applications and platforms, still as hardware and services to assist firms improve their processes. Oracle's applications focus on enterprise resource data management, collaboration, planning, application development, customer relationship management, and provide chain management.

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